

Detecting Road Network Change from OpenStreetMap History: A Multiscale Cascade Random Forest Approach

Kilian Mayer¹

¹ School of Geographical Sciences, University of Bristol, Bristol, United Kingdom

Correspondence: Kilian Mayer (kilian.mayer.2018@bristol.ac.uk)

Abstract. OpenStreetMap edit history is used to detect real-world road extensions via a multiscale cascade Random Forest validated against Ordnance Survey change snapshots and supporting transferable 1 km mapping of road developments.

Submission Type. model; algorithm; dataset;

BoK Concepts. [AM10] Data mining, [AM14] Generalization and aggregation, [GD4] Data Quality, Metadata and Data Infrastructure

Keywords. VGI, spatio-temporal change detection, transport infrastructure investment

1 Introduction

Tracing the development of transport networks and identifying when and where specific changes occur is central to research on the distribution, drivers, and effects of transport infrastructure investments. However, much empirical work relies on highly aggregated datasets derived from infrastructure inventories or government expenditures, which often obscure the timing and location of individual network extensions and make cross-regional comparisons difficult. This contribution, therefore, develops an approach to infer road-network extensions from OpenStreetMap (OSM) by exploiting its full edit history.

OSM is widely used as a spatial data source, yet its temporal dimension remains comparatively underutilised. In many developed countries, road-network completeness reached mature levels in the early 2010s, creating conditions under which a growing share of subsequent edits plausibly reflects real-world transport infrastructure investments rather than initial mapping alone (Haklay, 2010; Barrington-Leigh and Millard-Ball, 2017; Juhász,

2021). Building on this observation, the study asks whether changes visible in OSM history can be used to infer real-world road-network extensions and, if so, whether a model trained in the UK can be transferred to Germany and France to map the spatial distribution of road development over time.

2 Methods

2.1 Reference outcome and spatial-temporal framework

Model training and validation are performed using authoritative reference data for the UK based on versioned snapshots of Ordnance Survey (OS) MasterMap Highways RoadLink (2017–2023). Successive OS snapshots are compared, and changes are aggregated to a 1 km × 1 km grid for annual periods. A cell-period is labelled as “significant extension” if OS road length increases by more than 50 m during the period. This creates a binary outcome that is used to train a Random Forest classifier.

2.2 OSM predictors from mapping history

For the OSM branch, the full history file is filtered for road features and the historical geometries are reconstructed to create temporal snapshots for the same dates as the OS snapshots. These snapshots are intersected with the same 1 km grid and converted into per-cell road-length deltas. Detailed OS and OSM classes are grouped into two broad categories, roads and roads_unclassified, focusing on arterial roads that are relevant to the overall network. The machine-learning predictors are derived from two underlying types of information in the OSM history data: the mapped length of relevant road features and the mapped length of highway=construction features.

From these, the model derives measures of total road stock, road-length change, construction completion, construction activity, and rate-based normalisations for each grid cell and period.

2.3 Multiscale cascade Random Forest

A Random Forest model is used to predict whether OS-observed growth in the road network occurred in each 1 km grid cell using only the OSM-derived predictors. A central challenge is separating coherent real-world construction signals from isolated mapping noise. The approach therefore implements a multiscale cascade: identical predictors are computed at three spatial aggregation levels, where 1 km cells are grouped into coarser “supergrids”. The three levels correspond to the 1 km grid ($f = 1$), 4 km \times 4 km supergrids ($f = 16$), and 8 km \times 8 km supergrids ($f = 64$). Random Forest models are trained at each level, and coarse predictions are propagated back to the 1 km grid via the parent–child relationship between supergrids and fine cells.

2.4 Validation and transfer

To reduce inflated performance estimates caused by spatial dependence between neighbouring grid cells, the final model uses a spatial holdout design in which training, validation, and test sets are separated using coarse supergrids rather than random cell-level splits. This follows the logic of location-based validation discussed by Meyer et al. (2018), but is implemented here by assigning larger spatial blocks to different samples. Training is rebalanced by oversampling the positive class, while test data retain original prevalence. After UK validation, the trained model will be applied without retraining to Germany and France to generate 1 km estimates of likely road-network extensions for 2015–2023. Credibility will be assessed by comparing aggregated predictions with official road length statistics (Eurostat, 2024).

2.5 Data and Software Availability

OpenStreetMap full-history data are publicly available from OpenStreetMap Contributors (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2026). OS MasterMap Highways RoadLink snapshots were accessed under licence, for example via EDINA Digimap (Ordnance Survey, 2017–2023), and therefore cannot be redistributed. The code used to produce the reported results will be made available at: <https://github.com/kilianmayergeo/osm-road-change-agile2026>

3 Results

The standard Random Forest achieved moderate discrimination on the held-out test split (ROC AUC 0.863; PR AUC 0.387), with precision, recall, and F1 all equal to 0.410 for the positive class. A three-stage cascade evaluated with a random 1 km cell-level split performed substantially better (ROC AUC 0.959; PR AUC 0.783; precision 0.642; recall 0.734; F1 0.685), but this design still allows neighbouring cells with similar spatial structures to fall into different samples. Under the stricter spatial holdout design, the final cascade achieved an accuracy of 0.936, ROC AUC of 0.889, PR AUC of 0.463, precision of 0.452, recall of 0.492, and F1 of 0.471. These lower but more robust results show that OSM history contains usable signals for detecting real-world road-network extensions when combined with multiscale aggregation.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The author declares that generative AI tools were used only for language support and editorial refinement during manuscript preparation. No AI tools were used to generate scientific claims, research data, model outputs, or substantive conclusions. All analysis, interpretation, and scientific judgments remain the sole responsibility of the author.

Acknowledgements

The author gratefully acknowledges PhD funding provided through the South West Doctoral Training Partnership (SWDTP) at the University of Bristol. This work was supported by the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) [grant number ES/P000630/1].

References

- Barrington-Leigh, C. and Millard-Ball, A.: The world’s user-generated road map is more than 80% complete, *PLOS ONE*, 12, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0180698>, 2017.
- Eurostat: Road length by type (NUTS 2), dataset, accessed [19/01/2025], 2024.
- Haklay, M.: How good is volunteered geographical information? A comparative study of OpenStreetMap and Ordnance Survey datasets, *Environ. Plan. B*, 37, 682–703, <https://doi.org/10.1068/b35097>, 2010.
- Juhász, L.: Towards understanding the temporal accuracy of OpenStreetMap: A quantitative experiment, in: *Proceedings of the Academic Track, State of the Map 2021*, pp. 19–22, 2021.

Meyer, H., Reudenbach, C., Hengl, T., Katurji, M., and Nauss, T.: Improving performance of spatio-temporal machine learning models using forward feature selection and target-oriented validation, *Environ. Model. Softw.*, 101, 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2017.12.001>, 2018.

OpenStreetMap Contributors: United Kingdom extract [united-kingdom-internal.osh.pbf], Geofabrik Download Server, available at: <https://osm-internal.download.geofabrik.de/europe/united-kingdom-internal.osh.pbf> (contains OSM data up to 2026-03-29T20:21:06Z, last access: 4 April 2026), 2026.

Ordnance Survey (GB): OS MasterMap Highways Network [GML3 geospatial data], accessed under institutional licence via EDINA Digimap, snapshots 2017–2023, last access: 4 April 2026, n.d.